

Intangible Cultural Heritage of Algeria (Traditional Industries and Crafts)

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Abstract

Intangible cultural heritage is one of the basic sources that allow individuals and societies to know their history and identity. It includes practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills as well as the instruments, objects, artefacts... as their nature and function reveal the ancient history of peoples. To preserve this identity, it is necessary to preserve this heritage.

The Algerian cultural heritage is full of many crafts and traditional industries that are threatened with extinction and erasure from popular memory due to the tyranny of modern industries and the lack of interest in them.

Traditional industries and crafts play an important role in the development of the economy at the global level, so Algeria must also promote this sector and pay some attention to its participation in the development of the national economic sector.

This study aims to highlight the intangible cultural heritage of Algeria (traditional industries and crafts). It represents an important sector, as it expresses the identity of people and the culture of a nation. It is considered an important economic activity that has contributed to the development and growth of craft activities at all levels.

Through a literature review of intangible cultural heritage and traditional crafts and industries, after that the types of traditional crafts and industries in Algeria; which are: the textile industry, leather industry, pottery industry and jewelry industry..., at the last the proposition of the most important mechanisms for developing this traditional industries and crafts in Algeria.

Currently, the traditional industries and crafts have become an important vital sector, contributing to the formation of the country's gross domestic product.

Keywords: Cultural Heritage, Intangible Cultural Heritage, Traditional Industries, Crafts, Algeria.

Introduction

Tangible and intangible cultural heritage of countries is a witness to the civilizations that passed through and left their mark on their territory, and the central basis for writing the history of these nations and countries, it expresses their identity, self and history. Traditional industries play an important role in the development of tourism in many countries, accounting for 10% of tourism revenues according to the World Tourism Organization, so Algeria should also promote this sector and pay some attention to its involvement in the development of the national economy.

This study aims to highlight the intangible cultural heritage of Algeria (traditional industries and crafts). It represents an important sector, as it expresses the identity of people and the culture of a nation. It is considered an important economic activity that has contributed to the development and growth of craft activities at all levels.

The importance of the research comes in providing effective solutions to promote the traditional industries and crafts sector to be exploited in the development and promotion of national economic sector, through the creation and promotion of markets, in addition to improving and developing means of work and other solutions aimed at developing this field.

The research dictates those traditional industries play an essential role in the development of the national economic sector and contribute to increasing the national income of the country, by developing it while preserving the national identity in its symbols.

Literature Review

Intangible Cultural Heritage Definition

The "intangible cultural heritage" means the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills – as well as the instruments, objects, artefacts and cultural spaces associated therewith – that communities, groups and, in some cases, individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage. This

intangible cultural heritage, transmitted from generation to generation, is constantly recreated by communities and groups in response to their environment, their interaction with nature and their history, and provides them with a sense of identity and continuity, thus promoting respect for cultural diversity and human creativity. For the purposes of this Convention, consideration will be given solely to such intangible cultural heritage as is compatible with existing international human rights instruments, as well as with the requirements of mutual respect among communities, groups and individuals, and of sustainable development [1].

The “intangible cultural heritage”, as defined in paragraph 1 above, is manifested inter alia in the following domains:

- (a) Oral traditions and expressions, including language as a vehicle of the intangible cultural heritage;
- (b) Performing arts;
- (c) Social practices, rituals and festive events;
- (d) Knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe;
- (e) Traditional craftsmanship [1].

Traditional Industries and Crafts Definition

UNESCO defines Traditional Industries and Crafts as follows:

Products that are produced by artisans, either completely by hand or with the help of hand-tools or even mechanical means, as long as the direct manual contribution of the artisan remains the most substantial component of the finished product... The special nature of artisanal products derives from their distinctive features, which can be utilitarian, aesthetic, artistic, creative, culturally attached, decorative, functional, traditional, religiously and socially symbolic and significant” [2].

According to the *World Craft Council's in 2019*. It is useful to view craft in two defined and linked aspects defined below:

A. Traditional and heritage crafts encompass the skilled making of objects utilising materials including clay, fibre, metal, glass and wood and calling on traditions and histories handed down through generations

B. Contemporary craft is the skilled making of objects. It is an intellectual and physical activity whereby the maker explores the infinite possibilities of materials and processes to produce unique and expressive forms [3].

Traditional craft industries are economic sectors that produce handmade goods using traditional methods passed down through generations. These industries often rely on skilled artisans who create unique products tied to a particular culture or region [4].

Traditional Industries and Crafts in Algeria

Algeria has a rich and diverse stock of distinctive traditional products, which were formed or are being shaped by the influence of a number of factors, most notably traditions, which in turn differ from one region to another in addition to the successive influence of long-lived civilizations in Algeria, where Algerian traditional products vary between clothing, furnishings, jewelry, household items and even food [5].

Below are the most important traditional industries in Algeria, in addition to the most important regions that are famous for their production:

Carpets industry: It relies mainly on natural raw materials based on wool and natural colors extracted from herbs and plants. Among the most famous Algerian carpets, we find the Jabal Ammour carpet in the Aflou region (Laghouat), Babbar carpet in the Khenchela region, the Beni Yazguen carpet in Ghardaia.....etc [5].

Leather industry: The leather industry is characterized by its connection to livestock raising areas, which are considered the basis of the raw material (leather). Among the most prominent products of this industry, we find saddles, shoes, belts, and wallets [5].

Copper industry: Its origin goes back to the Ottoman presence. Copper products are similar and differ from one region to another in terms of the nature of the product, as well as the inscriptions and symbols used. Among the cities famous for this industry, we find Algiers, specifically in the Coppersmiths' Street in the ancient Kasbah, as well as Constantine and Tlemcen [5].

Jewelry industry: Various regions of the country are famous of this type of activity, as we find it in the Awras, Constantine, Kabylie and Hoggar countries, where Awras jewelry is mostly made of silver and is distinguished by the precision of the engravings, such as the silver belt [5].

Traditional Embroidery: Embroidery on cloth is an elegant traditional craft that is characteristic of various Algerian cities and is evident in various beautiful traditional dresses, such as the caftan, the karako and the Kabyle dress...[5].

Basketry industry: It includes the manufacture of mats, gabions, furniture, etc., Among the most important areas famous for this industry are the desert areas, the Kabylie region, and other cities that still maintain this industry despite the many obstacles and challenges it faces.

Pottery industry: The pottery industry relies on clay. Among the regions famous for its pottery industry; we find the Kabylie region, the Auras and the Mزاب Valley [5].

Figure 1. Carpets industry [6]

Figure 2. Copper industry [7]

Figure 3. Jewellery industry [8]

Figure 4. Pottery industry [9]

The Importance of Traditional Industries and Crafts in the Valorization of Heritage

Traditional industries represent an important sector with cultural, economic, social and tourism dimensions, as it represents an important economic tributary and a living element of culture and civilization. It serves as documentary evidence of the cultural and historical components. It is one of the components of the national character, as it contributes to communication between the past and the present to consolidate identity, establish the spirit of authenticity, highlight heritage, and contribute to advancing economic and social development. As it constitutes an essential tributary with the goods and services it provides that are directly related to the life of citizens and in creating job opportunities with guaranteed income, by operating the capital in active ways and generating great profits for the state and great publicity and fame for tourism [10].

Traditional industries are also considered necessary for industrial, economic and social growth due to the increase in production and national income they achieve, in addition to covering part of the local markets, reducing imports and opening areas for export. It reflects an aspect of national identity and is an effective tool in preserving heritage [10].

Concerning and supporting traditional industries from extinction and creating a new vision and formal and functional formulations gives them a role in the development process of Algerian society.

Traditional crafts and industries are considered the most important components of the national character of peoples because they characterize the specificity and originality of society, and also express the cultural product of man interacting with his nature. This sector occupies a great position in the economy due to its effective role at various levels, which are:

The cultural and civilizational level: The cultural dimension has special importance for traditional crafts and industries, as it is considered a fundamental determinant of the purchasing decision for the national and foreign consumer, as the traditional product is considered a means of communication between members of society through the signs and lines drawn on it and an information bank for the various civilizations and societies that have passed through the country. Therefore, preserving traditional craftsmanship is the core of preserving the heritage of our ancestors and is also considered a symbol of

the moral character of every nation, which has made every country attach great importance to this cultural element [10].

The social and economic levels: The sector has the ability to absorb unemployment and create jobs. It also has a role in taking care of youth, which makes it a contributor to preserving this category of forms of deviance, so that traditional crafts and industries generate added value to the national income, and provide job opportunities for male and female segments of society, and thus contribute to the development of the economy and stimulating the productive and marketing movement. The sector has a competitive advantage due to the distinctiveness of the craft product from one region to another, and craft institutions have a role in raw local production and absorbing unemployment [10].

Traditional crafts are a practical and cultural system that usually arises from an ancient example. The methods of performance have varied throughout the ages depending on what happens to society with its customs, traditions, and needs for change and transformation. Studying crafts from the point of view of anthropology with a historical view of the structure of these crafts contributes to understanding the nature of life in our societies and knowing how to perform this craft and the extent of its prosperity [10].

Traditional Industries and Crafts Challenges in Algeria

Traditional industry is considered one of the most important components of the national economy as it contributes to the process of economic development by influencing the volume of national production, eliminating unemployment, foreign trade, and also plays an important role in tourist attraction [11].

However, many studies have proven the extent of the backwardness of this sector, given the problems and challenges that the industry suffers from, most notably financing problems, competition, regulatory stability, etc., which will be explained in the following points:

- The failure of including the traditional industry and crafts sector as a development priority within the country's economic and reform policies, and the weakness of clear legislation and laws to regulate and support it.
- Poor conditions for practicing craft activity;
- Difficulty in supplying raw materials and equipment;
- Limited training and skills development programmes
- Weak fiscal and tax stimulus
- The deficiencies in the established information system
- The lack of studies and the weakness of associational organizations which affect the development of the traditional industry and crafts sector.
- The high financial costs of participating at regional, national and even international salons by craftsmen.

These problems and difficulties negatively affected the sector's profitability, preventing the achievement of the set objectives in terms of quantity and quality. Which prompted the state to explore ways and find solutions to these problems and challenges by establishing a group of programs and bodies for the sake of developing the sector [11].

Mechanisms for Developing Traditional Industries and Crafts in Algeria

In an effort to advance the traditional industry sector, the state has made significant efforts to achieve this through financial support and moral incentives granted to craftsmen, in addition to establishing development programs for the sector [12].

Support and promotion structures: It plays the role of supervisor of the traditional industry sector in Algeria, ensuring the management and development of the traditional industry sector. It can be divided into national and local structures [12].

A. National structures: It includes the National Chamber of Traditional Industry and the National Agency for Traditional Industry [12].

- National Chamber of Traditional Industry: It is a public institution of an industrial and commercial nature, enjoying legal personality and financial independence, and placed under the supervision of the Minister in charge of traditional industry. It is a forum for representation of craft professions [12].
- National Agency for Traditional Industry: It is a public institution of an industrial and commercial nature that has a legal personality and financial independence. It aims to preserve, promote, revitalize and develop activities related to traditional and artistic industries [12].

B. Local Structures: It includes rooms for traditional industry and crafts, in addition to various spaces.

- Traditional industry and crafts rooms: The chambers are a real forum for representing craft professions at the local level and a judiciary that brings together the administration, craftsmen and their representatives. One of its most important tasks is to register craftsmen, support them, and accompany them in the process of qualification, product development and marketing, in addition to creating spaces, activities, and economic demonstrations that contribute to local development [12].
- Other various spaces: They are spaces run by chambers of traditional industry and crafts, where the role of traditional industry is represented by purchasing centres, traditional crafts centres, local skills centres, training and production workshops, carpet manufacturing centres, marketing centres, display and sales centres, excellence centres, technical centres...

Promotional or training programs: It aims to help craftsmen create their projects and ensure their success. Perhaps the most important of these programs are the following:

A. Software that creates and improves your enterprise Cree/Germe: It is a special training program to support the establishment and management of small enterprises, developed by the International Labor Organization. It provides an integrated methodology in training and methods used successfully at the global level, directed to the creators and managers of small enterprises. It aims to support the structures for promoting this type of enterprise, as well as towards continuous improvement of the enterprise process. Small and medium-sized enterprises through the training of project owners or enterprise managers [12].

B. Local Production Program: It is an effective organizational pattern through which work is coordinated and unified between artisans, their public environment, and sector support structures, in order to develop artisan production and overcome problems and difficulties [12].

C. Program Nucleus: To support the synergy of craftsmen, this program came within the framework of cooperation between Algeria and Germany. It aims to synergize craftsmen who practice the same activity. It was developed in cooperation with the German Technical Development Agency [12].

Financial support structures: Within the framework of the policy of reviving private investments and promoting small and medium enterprises in general and craft enterprises of an artisanal nature in particular, and for the purpose of encouraging individual initiatives and self-employment, the government has allocated a set of structures and financial support programs that would provide economic and technical advice and financial assistance to craftsmen [12].

Promotional events to promote the traditional industry: Whether at the local, regional, national or even international levels, it aims to promote the local product, including:

- Celebrating the National Handicraft Day.
- Local and national salons.
- International Salon of Traditional Crafts.
- Organizing Algerian traditional industry weeks abroad.
- Creating the National Award for Traditional Industry and Crafts [12].

Conclusion

Traditional industries and crafts sector have known many developments both in terms of materials or used techniques. These industries know many problems and difficulties that threaten to disappear, among the measures that must be taken are the following:

- Working to allocate special prizes for craft creativity.
- The need to organize the traditional industry and crafts sector by following the best management approaches.
- The necessity of having, establishing and encouraging specialized centers for training in traditional craft industries to transfer it to future generations.
- Working to enhance the qualifications of craftsmen in order to provide competitive products in the market.
- Holding periodic meetings with bodies and departments related to the traditional industry and crafts sector.

These proposals were brought from the problems that threaten the traditional industries and crafts to disappear, therefore the main objective that we wish to be applied in reality is to highlight the intangible cultural heritage of Algeria (traditional industries and crafts) for the development of craft activities at all levels.

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